

The Circles of Mobility: A Holistic Exploration of Mobility Behaviours in The Netherlands

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Summary

This project seeks to characterise Dutch neighbourhoods by analysing observed mobility behaviours. Grounded in a multi-layer theoretical framework, we investigate the impact of individual and environmental factors on mobility. Our analysis considers four spheres of influence: individual demographics, household characteristics, built environment features, and access to services and job opportunities. Combining Census data with the Dutch national travel survey, we generate a synthetic dataset at the neighbourhood level. This dataset delineates each spatial unit across our predefined four levels of influence, accompanied by a layer detailing the most common mobility behaviours in the area.

KEYWORDS: Mobility behaviours, Spatial Justice, Accessibility, Spatial Analysis.

1 Introduction and Background

Mobility behaviours encompass the diverse ways individuals move, travel, or interact with transportation systems in their daily lives. Motivations for these movements can span from commuting to work, engaging in leisure activities, or fulfilling care-related responsibilities. While traditional transport literature has predominantly emphasised commuting, there is a growing recognition of the importance of studying mobility behaviours in the context of various activities (Charreire et al., 2021). This is particularly pertinent considering the multitude of activities individuals undertake beyond work, some of which are still linked to specific segments of the population. For example, extensive research has delved into the intricacies of women’s activity chains and modal usage, revealing a heightened complexity associated with their traditionally significant time allocation to

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childcare, eldercare, and household-related tasks (Scheiner and Holz-Rau, 2017). Moreover, mobility behaviours inherently possess a spatial dimension. Limited access to opportunities translates to a constrained range of transport modes available to individuals and influences the associated costs. This spatial aspect gains significance in light of recent findings indicating that the most disadvantaged communities tend to experience lower access to essential services (Calafiore et al., 2022; Nicoletti et al., 2022).

Transport research literature emphasises the importance of recognising the complex nature of travel decisions by acknowledging the multitude of factors influencing mobility behaviours. Traditionally, these factors are categorised into two primary groups: internal and external factors (Scheiner and Holz-Rau, 2007). Internal factors encompass features intrinsic to the individual and their personal circumstances, such as sex (Havet et al., 2021; Scheiner and Holz-Rau, 2017), household composition (Yang et al., 2017), or car ownership (Ding et al., 2017). Conversely, external factors represent the elements that characterise the environment in which individuals lead their daily lives. This includes urban form (Ewing and Cervero, 2010), local access to services (Lee et al., 2017), or the quality of the public transport system in the area (Ryan and Wretstrand, 2019).

The intricate interplay between internal and external factors adds complexity to determining the dominant aspects in travel decisions (Scheiner and Holz-Rau, 2007). Within this context, we propose a different approach to analysing travel behaviour in association to a person’s intrinsic and extrinsic factors, linking an individual to their household, neighbourhood and regional contexts. Termed the Circles of Influence theory (see Figure 1), our framework posits the existence of four layers of factors influencing an individual’s mobility behaviours. These factors encompass the individual themselves, the household they reside in, their immediate surroundings (such as the built environment), and their access to regional opportunities.

Our paper aims at generating a country-level, high spatial resolution data frame to capture all the multi-level factors affecting mobility decisions in the context of The Netherlands. Our analysis will, additionally, combine all these factors with real mobility data extracted from the Dutch national travel survey to estimate the most common mobility behaviours at neighbourhood level. This cross-scale dataset will allow us to disentangle how an individual’s mobility behaviours are associated with their multi-level socio-economic and built environment indicators. Overall, this work not only provides valuable insights for understanding mobility patterns in The Netherlands but also lays a foundation for tailored policymaking, enabling the formulation of targeted strategies to enhance transportation infrastructure and address specific mobility challenges at different scales.

2 Methods and Data

In this paper, we employ a multi-step methodology to comprehensively characterise neighbourhoods across The Netherlands. Firstly, we integrate four distinct data frames to represent the four spheres of influence described in our theoretical framework: 1) individual characteristics; 2) household characteristics; 3) neighbourhood attributes; and 4) access to opportunities in the regional context. Figure 2 illustrates the flowchart guiding the collection and processing of all data sets employed in

Figure 1: Circles of influence.

the analysis¹.

We derived individuals' demographic features from the 2019 Census data Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2023). The 2019 Census was preferred as it provided the latest, most complete data for all the variables required. Selected features included age, sex, ethnic background, educational attainment, and occupational status. Similarly, household characteristics were obtained from the 2019 Census, and included information on household income, car availability and household composition. To align the data with the desired spatial resolution (4-digit postcodes or PC4), we applied areal average weighting. Figure 3 shows the process employed to convert census data from its original spatial unit -Buurt- to PC4. In this example, we observe the case of a PC4 that contains several subareas of different Buurten. The value we input to the PC4 results from averaging the values of the variable at Buurt level and weighting them by the proportion of the area within the PC4.

Our characterisation of the built environment hinges on two key features: urbanity level and local accessibility. Urbanity level, which ranges from 'very urban' to 'not urban', is a measure of area density determined by the number of postal addresses per square kilometre, as per Census data Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (2023). On the other hand, local accessibility assesses the availability of essential amenities -schools, supermarkets, GPs, pharmacies, parks, and public transport stops- within a 20-minute walk from the centroid of each 4-digit postcode. We calculated the cumulative access metric employing data from OpenStreetMap OpenStreetMap Contributors (2017) and the R library r5r Pereira et al. (2021).

¹All data sets are open, with the exception of travel survey data (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2022), which can however be accessed under request.

Figure 2: Data processing flowchart.

The final layer of our framework evaluates each postcode’s connectivity to regional job opportunities. We began by calculating travel times via public transport and car from each postcode to all potential job destinations. Next, we used observed commuting flows to weight these travel times, with the weight of each connection determined by the proportion of commuters travelling from the origin to the destination. In line with previous studies in the field (Marin et al., 2022; Lowe, 1998), we used these weighted travel times as input for an entropy metric. This metric quantifies the diversity of potential job destinations accessible from each origin (Equations 1 and 2). The key advantage of using entropy to gauge the complexity of commuting networks lies in its simultaneous assessment of variety and balance. This allows for a more nuanced evaluation of regional connectivity.

$$H = - \sum_{i,j=1}^n t_{ij} w_{ij} \log(t_{ij} w_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

where:

$$w_{ij} = \frac{f_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i} \quad (2)$$

Mobility behaviours were extracted leveraging multiple rounds (2018-2022) of Onderweg in Nederland (ODiN), the Dutch national travel survey. This data set provides country-wide information about daily mobility behaviours of individuals in The Netherlands. Similarly to other studies employing this data set Poorthuis and Zook (2023), combining several rounds of the survey allowed us to expand the number of observations to approximately 200,000 individuals over the expanse of five years. For each individual we extracted a set of variables from the survey: main travel mode, modal mix, activity chain complexity, time spent travelling to destinations, and time spent per activity category. Following other studies in Transport literature Anable (2005); Victoriano et al. (2020), we grouped individuals in the survey based on how similar their mobility behaviours were. We employed a k-means algorithm to perform the clustering.

Figure 3: Example of overlap between 4-digit postcodes and Buurten.

The final step in our methodology involves the assessment of the importance of each factor in determining mobility behaviours. The framing of our theoretical background together with the nature of our data, leads us to propose the development of a Bayesian multi-level model where each block of variables -individual, household, neighbourhood, and region- represents a different level in the model. A Bayesian approach to the modelling was preferred due to the more intuitive interpretability of the model results and the possibility that this framework offers to quantify uncertainty.

Figure 4: Examples of data sets employed in the analysis in The Hague. Maps showing samples of individual (income per inhabitant), household (cars per household) and built environment (local access to schools)

3 Results and Discussion

Our preliminary results have provided us with a comprehensive data frame that comprises all the layers to be employed in our analysis. Figure 4 provides an overview of three of the variables employed to characterise Dutch neighbourhoods at three different levels: individual, household, and built environment. The first variable represents the average income per inhabitant in PC4s of The Hague, showcasing an example of individual-level data. The second variable, car ownership -household level variable-, presents higher in suburban areas than in the city centre, as expected given the likely lower access to public transport the further we move from the urban core. Finally, the last circle shows one of the components of the built environment: local access to services. Specifically, in this visualisation we focus on access to schools within a 20 minute walk.

Figure 5: Entropy was used as a metric to assess neighbourhood accessibility to job opportunities. We employed weighted travel times by car and public transport to every other neighbourhood in the country, using the proportion of people commuting from each origin to each destination as leveraging factor to assess the relative importance of each connection.

Figure 5 shows the entropy of outbound workflows for each postcode in the country. The metric was calculated as the entropy of weighted travel times from each postcode to all potential work destinations. The weights represent the relative importance of each connection, and are based on the proportion of people from each postcode that are employed in each destination. Intuitively, regions where commuting flows are highly concentrated into few destinations will show lower entropy than regions where flows are more evenly distributed. Interestingly, our results depict an urban hierarchy where main cities like Amsterdam, The Hague, Rotterdam, Utrecht, and Groningen and their corresponding commuting zones are classified as high-entropy zones. On the other hand, more disconnected areas such as Maastricht are classified as low-entropy regions.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents a new approach to analyse the relationship between mobility behaviours and accessibility based on an individual's socio-economic demographics. Transport literature has widely explored the plethora of factors affecting travel decisions, and why understanding the complex inter-relationships between them is key for effective policy making (Scheiner and Holz-Rau, 2007). Our work aims at generating a country-wide high spatial resolution data set for The Netherlands where a comprehensive set of factors -individual, household, built environment, and access to opportunities- is assessed and employed for generating neighbourhood-level mobility behaviours. We expect the outcomes of this research to aid decision-makers at the time of applying data-driven transport policies, providing them with nuanced information at a very high resolution level. From a social justice point of view, we consider that this research can also be very valuable at the time of uncovering inequalities in access to opportunities, particularly among most disadvantaged groups. Future steps will focus on the generation of neighbourhood-level mobility behaviours using a combination of travel survey data and the different data sets derived from the first phase of our methodology, followed by a detailed multi-level spatial analysis of how individuals exhibit mobility behaviours based on their household, neighbourhood and regional characteristics.

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